

Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center

2023-24 Seed Grant Program Final Report

Perceptions of Earthquakes by Olympic Peninsula, Washington, Visitors and Residents

Carol F. Sawyer, University of South Alabama

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Project title: Perceptions of Earthquakes by Olympic Peninsula, Washington, Visitors and Residents

This project aimed to identify differences in perceptions of risk from earthquakes and tsunamis originating from the Cascadia Subduction Zone (CSZ) between residents of the North Olympic Peninsula and tourists visiting or who have visited the region. Undergraduate students were recruited to assist with the project, to expose them to field research, and to increase undergraduate participation in geohazards research.

Pre-trip preparations

A questionnaire was developed using Qualtrics, a cloud-based platform. The University of South Alabama's Institutional Review Board (IRB) approved the survey for public distribution. A request was made to the National Park Service to share the study with visitors of Olympic National Park, but the NPS declined the permit request. The Native American Tribal administration also declined to participate in the survey. The North Olympic Library System (<https://www.nols.org/>) agreed to help promote the study at each branch. Additionally, the Clallam County Emergency Management Office promoted the survey to its residents.

Student recruitment

Students were recruited through announcements for large (>50 students) general education courses taught by the principal investigator. Interested students were asked to complete a Google Form outlining expectations, including traveling for 7 days, flying to Washington State, and being comfortable asking strangers to participate in the survey. The five students who applied and agreed to these expectations included four Geography majors and one Education major. Two of these students will, upon graduation, be first-generation graduates. Among them, four were female, and two identified as Black and Native American. Only one student had flown more than three times, while two had never flown, and one had flown only once. Two students had never left the Southeastern U.S., and none had visited the Pacific Northwest. The students ranged in age from 19 to 23.

Student experiences

Care was taken to build students' confidence during the experience by providing packing lists with expected weather conditions, links to our lodging, and a detailed itinerary. Students were required to complete Human Subjects Protection training, which certified them to administer questionnaires. An added benefit of this training is that they can include it on their resumes. Students received a short lecture on what the CSZ was, how an earthquake from the CSZ could impact the northern Olympic Peninsula, and the expected inundation zones of a tsunami.

Post-trip, students were asked to provide feedback on their field experience. Overall, the fieldwork was a highly successful and impactful activity that not only offered practical

research skills but also boosted participants' confidence, clarified their future goals, and fostered a greater appreciation for teamwork and the natural environment. When comparing their expectations with their actual experiences, students reported that the reality of the experience greatly surpassed or differed from their initial feelings or fears. One participant initially struggled to explain the project and faced parental resistance but described the experience as "fantastic." Another mentioned being nervous about the plane ride, which turned out to be smooth, and now they are eager to fly again. Reflecting on what they learned about themselves, one student discovered they enjoy and are good at working closely with others. In contrast, another student was motivated to figure out who they want to become, which inspired them to work toward that goal. Another rediscovered a love for being outdoors, especially in cool, picturesque environments, which contrasts with where they currently live, confirming a deep enjoyment of the natural world. The students agreed that the experience positively influenced their outlook on future academic and career pursuits. The field experience made opportunities such as research, internships, and graduate school feel less intimidating, more appealing, and achievable. The most rewarding parts included personal connections with other students and locals, as well as the chance to travel and explore new environments. A few students emphasized that a key reward was having genuine and meaningful conversations with people being surveyed, especially when those individuals showed interest in the project and shared their stories.

Fieldwork Experience

The trip involved seven people: two professors (Sawyer and Mujica) and five students. Everyone traveled together to and from the airport and flew on the same flight to minimize nervousness. The itinerary focused on visiting communities within the study area to distribute the survey; however, we also explored several points of interest to help students understand the environment, how an earthquake and tsunami could impact the region, and how the current physical landscape was formed. All students had completed a freshman-level geomorphology course covering earthquake and tsunami hazard zones and glacial landscapes. During the fieldwork, students were asked to recall landforms from that course. They visited businesses in the following communities and asked workers to display the survey flyer (Figure 1). Additionally, students handed out flyers to people they met during their visits to the communities. To give an appearance of legitimacy, students wore matching CRESCENT T-shirts (Figure 2). Over 750 flyers were distributed during the trip. To encourage participation, refrigerator magnets (Figure 3) were also handed out to the public and businesses, with extra magnets and flyers given to the libraries, the Chamber of Commerce, and the Clallam County Emergency Office for distribution.

Communities where flyers were distributed

- Sequim
- Port Angeles
- Forks
- Sekiu
- Clallam Bay
- Joyce

Figure 6. Students visiting the Pacific Ocean for the first time.

Did you accomplish what you set out to with this project?

Primarily, yes. Exposing students to fieldwork and a different environment increased their interest in the geosciences. A greater understanding of the challenges and rewards of fieldwork has emerged within this cohort. Both students and researchers were disappointed that they were not allowed to ask visitors at Olympic National Park to participate in the survey. The survey responses are lower than expected without national park visitor participation. Students will continue to be involved in research projects, with a particular focus on first-generation students.

Next Steps

The questionnaire remains open and is expected to close in early January. The results will be presented at the 2026 Annual Meeting of the American Association of Geographers (AAG) in San Francisco, California, in March 2026, with all the students listed as co-authors. Three of the five students involved in the research project plan to attend the meeting and help present the results. The planned publication for the findings is the *Annals of the American Association of Geographers*. A presentation and possibly a publication are in development on survey response rates for surveys advertised through different methods (e.g., in-person vs. social media).